

TECHNICAL NOTE

Technical note: Individual characteristics in shoe outsoles resulting from recycled material components

Matthias Braune ^{1 2}

¹ Kriminaltechnisches Institut im
Landeskriminalamt Bremen, In der Vahr 76,
28329 Bremen, Germany
(engl.: Forensic Science Institute at the
State Criminal Police Office of Bremen)

² FSB - Forensisches Sachverständigenbüro
Braune, Malenter Str.8a, 28844 Weyhe,
Germany
(engl.: Forensic Expert Office Braune)

Correspondence

FSB - Forensisches Sachverständigenbüro
Braune, Dipl.-Ing. [FH] Dipl.-Verww. [FH]
Matthias Braune, Malenter Str.8a, 28844
Weyhe, Germany
E-Mail: mail@german-forensics.de

Funding information

FSB - Forensisches Sachverständigenbüro
Braune

Abstract

Report on individualizing characteristics in the outsoles of shoes that were identified during a forensic comparative examination at the Forensic Science Institute of the State Criminal Police Office in Bremen, Germany. The study focused on recycled flakes molded into the sole, some of which are located on the surface of the sole or inside the sole and are exposed when the shoes are worn, which can lead to unique characteristics in the shoe print. This information is intended for experts in shoe impression traces and shoe print traces in the context of their daily comparative work and is to expand their expertise and protect them from assessment errors. It supplements my script, which was created for the national German-language expert training program at the German Federal Criminal Police Office. There is also a note on similarly configured glove prints, which could potentially supplement my German glove print expertise.

This technical note could serve as the basis for a bachelor's thesis in the field of shoe prints and is intended to encourage students to conduct more intensive research in this area.

KEYWORDS

shoe prints, shoe impression marks, shoe comparison examination, individual characteristics, glove prints

About 25 years ago, I became aware of an African company that resoled shoes with old tire treads. At the time, I thought it was a good recycling idea. What I didn't know then was that as early as 1992, shoe manufacturer Nike had already begun considering ways to recycle shoes. Nike's initiative is now called "Nike Grind" and involves shredding individual shoe components into a kind of loose or fine material (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Nike Grind components [Advertisement by Nike]

Since 2009, other companies such as the German firms *Sorbas* and *Soex* have also jumped on the recycling way. *Soex* shreds shoes even further than Nike Grind, while *Sorbas* manufactures shoes from partially recycled materials.

Major German shoe manufacturers are still lagging behind in this regard. *Adidas*, for example, boasts that it uses 60% recycled polyester in its polyester materials, while *Puma* focuses solely on ecologically manufactured products and, like *Adidas*, uses 80% recycled polyester.

Until now, I have considered the efforts of environmentally conscious companies such as Nike to be commendable and exemplary. Old shoes were turned into new products such as rubber mats, floor coverings, artificial turf, and other everyday items. However, this was always a form of downcycling, because the recycled materials were no longer used to manufacture shoes.

However, during a shoe print comparison investigation in Bremen/Germany, I was confronted with reality and discovered that Nike, for example, now also manufactures soles that are visibly made from recycled materials. And not just in the midsole or insole, but explicitly in the tread area. To gain clarity about the special features of these soles, the outsoles of shoes from one shoe model were compared with each other. As suspected, the arrangement of the recycled components in the shoes compared was different, and I was able to assume that the outsole surface was unique.

Fig. 2: The object of investigation: Nike Air Max Alpha Trainer 5

The recycled components of this shoe (hereinafter referred to as flakes) were very small but immediately noticeable. Below is a microscopic image of the sole tread of the used shoe to be examined.

Fig. 3: Flakes in the outsole of a Nike Air Max Alpha Trainer 5

The left-hand image Fig. 3 shows the different colors of individual flake-like fillers, which were randomly distributed across the tread. However, it was also clear to see that the flakes were embedded and had

adapted to the manufacturing mold, particularly its surface, in the same way as the rest of the tread compound. It can therefore be assumed that the fillers would not be noticeable on a comparative track. However, if we recall the layer effect* described in the shoe script, the enclosed flakes could theoretically still lead to different imprint behavior.

In the comparative track creation carried out here, in addition to the usual damage, the above-mentioned investigation also focused on the position and visibility of the flakes in the comparative impression, knowing full well that evaluation could be difficult due to the very small flakes used in this shoe.

The comparative trace was initially created using biofluid and then contrasted with iron powder.

Deep black marks were noticeable in the comparative trace created with biofluid and iron powder, as would be expected with a layer effect (see image Fig. 4 below / green arrows).

Fig. 4: Deep black marks in the comparison track

These deep black marks were also found in other places. A subsequent comparison between the tread (mirrored) and the reference mark (biofluid/iron powder) revealed clear similarities (see comparison below).

Fig. 5: Comparative examination of mirrored original and comparison track

The cover-up procedure subsequently carried out using the Lucia Forensic software (bottom: sole / top: red, transparent comparison track) also revealed many matches that could be used for identification purposes.

Fig. 6: Covering method: comparative track and mirrored outsole [comparison with Lucia Forensic software]

It is therefore clear to me that the tiny flakes can be used for identification purposes if they are visible in the track.

When examining the individual tiny flakes, it was also noticeable that some of them appeared to be raised, i.e., they protruded from the actual sole material. One theory could be that the filler has a greater hardness, so that the sole material wears away more quickly around the filler. Another possible theory could be that the microflakes, which are merely embedded in the outsole compound and not firmly fused with it, break off more quickly.

Research was initiated to find out whether this type of recycling is also used in other shoes. So far, this process has only been found in Nike shoes. There are now many Nike shoes with tiny flakes, as a visit to a Nike store revealed. In images on the internet, the tiny flakes are usually not visible due to the resolution.

However, it is still unclear what proportion of the mixture consists of microflakes in relation to the actual sole material. It is also unclear how and when the microflakes are mixed with the sole material during the manufacturing process. There are therefore many factors that remain unclear.

However, it is important for the shoe print expert to determine whether there is any individuality. To this end, comparisons were made with shoes of the same model and size.

Figure 7 shows two Nike Court Vision shoes of the same pattern and size as examples.

Fig. 7: Different distribution of flakes on a Nike Court Vision

The distribution of the tiny white flakes visible here varied between the two shoes shown here and also between many other shoes of the same model. It can therefore be assumed that the distribution is unique in each shoe. The same uneven distribution was also observed in the following models:

Fig. 8: Model Nike Full Force

Fig. 9: Nike Air Max Flyknit Racer

Fig. 10: Nike Air Max 95

Fig. 11: Nike Revolution 6

The uneven distribution of tiny flakes on the tread was observed on all shoes of the same model and pattern. The use of tiny flakes is noticeable to the trained eye even when viewing the sole from the side. Through internet research, even more models were discovered and found in shoe stores. The terms associated with the model names were Grind and/or Crater. Here, visibly larger and more flakes were used.

The following list is not exhaustive and does not claim to be complete. It is intended solely to illustrate examples of use.

Fig. 12: Nike Air Max 90 Grind Black

Fig. 13: Nike Waffle Racer Crater (The shaft differs in color from the image of the sole)

Fig. 14: Nike Air Zoom Superrep - Next Nature

(It is not yet clear whether this shoe has a structured sole or an individual tread. However, some obvious 'thickening' that is not present in the 'standard' Air Force 1 models without flakes suggests that it is unique – green arrow.)

Fig. 15: Nike Air Force 1 (Crater)

Fig. 16: Nike Dunk Low (Crater) Grind

(It is not yet clear whether this shoe has a structured sole shape or whether it has a unique tread pattern. Some obvious structures that we could not identify in other images on the internet also suggest that this shoe is unique.)

Fig. 17: Nike Crater Impact

Fig. 18: Outsole Nike Crater Impact

Anyone familiar with the casting manufacturing process knows that shrinkage of the molded part usually occurs. If, as in this case, you imagine fillers in a molded part that are made of a different material, these flakes will behave differently from the surrounding sole material when the molded part shrinks. Thus, a flake with the appropriate dimensions can cause a small bump into the sole material, which means individuality (see Fig. 17). Similarly, a flake located on the outer surface can prevent the sole material from reaching the edge of the mold, leaving a partial void (see Fig. 18).

Fig. 19: Nike Air Zoom SuperRep 2

When touching the sole surface, I could feel irregularities in addition to the surface structure, which I took as an initial indication that some flakes were coming loose. Another shoe of the same model and size had a completely different flake structure, and no irregularities could be detected in the same places as on the shoe shown here.

Since no details were visible to the naked eye, I used a camera zoom to better interpret individual irregularities. A microscopic image would certainly have made the features more clearly visible, but I think the camera zoom already provides a good impression.

In this image, there are several flakes that protrude noticeably from the tread (red arrows).

There are also raised flakes on the base of the profile (red arrows).

A fissure can be seen around the shape of the black flake on the surface (red arrow). It could not be determined whether the fissure occurred during manufacture (e.g., shrinkage) or during a test run with the shoe.

Even in the edge area of a profile, a flake that had come loose could be seen on the shoe (red arrow).

Fig. 20: Flakes rising out of the sole

Furthermore, it should not be overlooked that wearing such shoes is likely to cause flakes close to the surface to fracture or possibly break off.

Summary

In accordance with the aforementioned characteristics, individualizing features may appear in a sole when recycled flakes are incorporated, as summarized in Fig. 20. These would be:

- a) The flake rises above the surface of the sole
- b) Cracks form along the embedded flake during use (due to material-related differences)
- c) The position of the embedded flake varies due to the flake loosening during use, resulting in a different imprint pattern
- d) The flake may break off during use
- e) The flake may break during use, resulting in a varying imprint pattern

- f) Due to possible material differences, the so-called “layer effect” results in varying imprint behavior (*layer effect: altered impression behavior with different material*)
- g) Wear on the sole exposes flakes (similar to other soles with embedded air bubbles).
- h) If the flakes are more voluminous than the ribs in a sole, these thickenings can result in a different impression in a track than with another sole.

Fig. 21: Possible individualizing characteristics through embedded flakes

After considering the results of this report, it can be concluded that the presence of (recycled) fillers in the form of flakes leads to individuality in a shoe tread.

In my opinion, further investigations should be carried out into these shoes. A bachelor's thesis could also be written on this topic. It is of utmost importance to determine validated results on possible uniqueness, as they can significantly influence the results of shoe print investigations.

Incidentally, Nike also works with the South Korean glove manufacturer Zi:ro. This company produces Thin Grip, Air Grip, Cushion Grip, and Thermo Grip gloves using Nike Grind. Further research into these gloves is also necessary to expand German research into glove marks in this field.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project was supported by funding from the Forensic Expert Office Braune and created in collaboration with the Criminal Investigation Department of the State Criminal Police Office of Bremen, Germany. The opinions, findings, conclusions, or recommendations expressed in this publication/program/exhibition are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect those of the State Criminal Police Office of Bremen.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Matthias Braune: Concept design; data curation; formal analysis; funding acquisition; investigation; methodology; project management; resources; supervision; visualization; writing the original draft and revising and editing the draft; validation

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author of this manuscript confirms that he has no connections to or interests in organizations or institutions that have financial or non-financial interests in the topics or materials covered in this manuscript. This is an informational transfer of scientific content from experts to experts.

STATEMENT ON DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

ORCID

Matthias Braune <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0219-4838>

How to cite this article: Braune, M. Individual characteristics in shoe outsoles resulting from recycled material components. In *Forensic Eng.* (Vol. 2026, Number 1, pp. 1–15). MB Art & Publishing Weyhe-Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18615016>